

Ifa Religious Group in Ibadan

By Abimbola Christianah Ayegboyin, Bowen University Iwo, Osun State

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Ifa Religious Group in Ibadan is a Yoruba indigenous group in Ibadan

Date Range: 1992 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Nigeria

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa

Nigeria, West Africa. Most Nigerian Pentecostals live in southern Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Abimbola, Wande, Ifá: An exposition of Ifá literary corpus. Ibadan: Oxford University Press, 1976.
- Source 2: Adegbindin, O., Ifá in Yoruba thought system. (Durham, NC: Carolina Academic Press, 2014)
- Source 3: Elebuibon, Ifayemi. Ifá: The Custodian of Destiny. Ibadan/Akure: IFÁ Traditional Publications, 2000.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.richtmann.org/journal/index.php/mjss/article/view/13835>
- Source 1 Description: This article examines the Ifa training system among Yoruba practitioners in Southwestern Nigeria which includes Ibadan as well. It discusses how Ifa knowledge involves mentorship or apprenticeship. It further explores how Ifa knowledge is presented via oral tradition.
- Source 2 URL: <https://doaj.org/article/351d78e925a43c482e002e5beec6108>
- Source 2 Description: This study discusses Ifa as having ethical principles that checks members' behaviors, governance and justice.

– Source 3 URL: <https://revistas.rcaap.pt/cea/article/view/8294>

– Source 3 Description: This study which primarily is a fieldwork explores the material culture of Ifa divination in Isale -Oyo.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://lagosmuseum.ng/items/0feb299a-a76b-4af0-b514-85134d323e36>

– Source 1 Description: Lagos Museum archive (PDF: Odu Ifa collection)

– Source 2 URL: <https://ifa.university/odu-ifa/>

– Source 2 Description: Ifa University digital corpus (full 256 Odu System Platform)

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.africabib.org/rec.php?RID=308339339>

– Source 3 Description: Academic Discussion on Ifa Corpus Digitization

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Ifa has long been in cultural contact with other religious traditions such as Christianity, Islam and African Indigenous Religions of neighboring ethnic groups.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Religious affiliation is typically established through birth\family tradition, initiation, divination and also through regular participation in rituals.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Many devotees are raised within families that practice Ifa or broader Yoruba Religion

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: A person may decide personally to begin consulting Ifa, practice ritual activities and devote themselves to the worship of Ifa.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Not by class as people from different social backgrounds are allowed to become devotees of Ifa.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: Religious affiliation is not assigned at a particular age. Unlike some religions that operate the formal age based initiation, Ifa affiliation can occur any time.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Both male and female can be devotees as people become affiliated through family

tradition, personal choice and initiation.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: This works for initiated members but not for general adherents.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Yes

Notes: In Ifa, religious affiliation can be influenced or assigned by several factors such as family lineage, personal choice, initiation and divination.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Ifa can recruit new members but not like it is done in other religions that may seek converts on a large scale.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Devotees receive some political support from traditional authorities but not standard sponsorship from the state.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: Apostasy is not a central concept in Ifa.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 2357

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: Numerically, the core followers (open disciples) of Ifa are not so much. However, there are lots of people in Yorubaland who consult the Ifa oracle secretly or in private though they openly profess to be Muslims or Christians.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There is the leader called Oba Iwa Bogunmbe, other male priests (babalawo), female priestess (yanifa) and elders.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The leadership hierarchy is flexible. This is usually based on experience, spiritual knowledge and authority.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: The leader who doubles as a king is called Oba Iwa Bogunmbe.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: There are other religious communities with leaders and there is a form of hierarchy among leaders.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 5

Notes: 1. Devotees 2. Initiates 3. Junior priests 4. Senior Priests 5. The head or chief priest
The hierarchy could exceed 5.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: They are able to communicate and interpret messages from spiritual forces.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Yes

Notes: Powers are passed from a leader to his apprentices who continue the line of Ifa priesthood after the demise of an old sage.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: Many times, individuals who rise to senior leadership positions are initiated and receive powers commensurate to the level of leadership they have now attained.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Usually through lineage inheritance, recognition and initiation.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: They can make mistakes during divination and interpret wrongly.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Followers do not always make charges of the leaders but this is not to say they do not have the voice or right to do so.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Other leaders could point the attention of a fellow leader to their wrong doing or mistakes.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: Though the leader is respected by his subordinates, they are not required to accept all his

pronouncements.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The scripture is not in a single written book form. There is the odu Ifa corpus as well as Ese Ifa (Ifa verses)

↳ Are they written:

– No

Notes: Originally Oral but there are modern transcriptions.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: There are myths associated with its origin.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Notes: Orunmila the central figure in Ifa religion is not the supreme being but the custodian of wisdom.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Ifa teachings are being revealed by other supernatural being,

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Ifa priests are the authority when it comes to the interpretation of Odu ifa (ifa corpus)

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– No

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: There are shrines, altars and sacred groves

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No standard measurable percentage

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 20000

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 60

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 30

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 20

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 15

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: There are different types of religious monumental architecture.

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: others like Divination and initiation ground (igbo Odu-Ifa) and sacred sites/rooms

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

- At home
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces

Notes: They are also on doors and altars

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: They include shrines, sacred streams/rivers, rocks, hills, crossroads and sacred groves.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Sacred sites are deliberately located in relation to : forests, groves, rivers, rocks, hills etc.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: People travel to these sacred sites for divination, festivals and healing.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: Not mandatory.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, human beings are not viewed as being made up of only the physical body called Ara. There is the soul which is called Ori and believed to survive bodily death.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: These spiritual aspects of human beings are believed to escape physical death, interact with spiritual forces and influence destiny.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The body is material while the spirit-mind known as the non material continues to exist after bodily death.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Belief in afterlife is present in Ifa religion.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Ifa religion describes the afterlife as being in the spiritual realm(Orun rere).

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: The afterlife is understood as existing in heaven which is not physical.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: Yes it is often described as above (Orun) in contrast to the physical world(aye).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Notes: The afterlife in Ifa is not generally conceived as below or the underworld.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Notes: Yoruba world view does not present the world as either being horizontal or vertical

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Yes

Notes: Other space means a non physical realm.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Ifa religion expresses reincarnation through the return of ancestors (as new born babies).

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: An ancestor can return as a new born baby.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes reincarnation can happen through animals like goats and dogs.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Notes: People are not believed to be reborn as stones, houses or any other object.

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors are often believed to live through their descendants or lineage.

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

Notes: Ifa religion does not relate reincarnation to karma. There is the belief that life is shaped through destiny.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: There are special treatments for the corpses of members which include: washing, special prayers and burying symbolic objects with them.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: It is not a practice in Ifa religion

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, bodies are not preserved through embalming.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion interment is a practice among devotees

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Notes: Corpses are usually not flexed

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, corpses are usually laid out on their backs

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Notes: This is not a practice in Ifa religion

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: Locations and ritual treatment differs in specific group of people such as kings

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: It is not a religious practice in Ifa tradition

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, corpses are not exposed to elements such as air drying. and exposure of dead bodies outdoors.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: Dead bodies are not exposed for consumption by animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: Ifa religion does not practice secondary burial.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: Animal sacrifice can take place but human sacrifice is no longer a contemporary practice.

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Some are buried with clothing, items connected with the deceased occupation, jewelries and ritual items.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Significant wealth items may be included in burials especially for high status people.

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Some wealth may be interred in Ifa religion for influential or high status individuals. Though this is optional and not a mandatory practice.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Yes

Notes: This can happen but not mandatory

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Grave goods such ritual objects, personal items and occupational tools may be included in Ifa burials but not mandatory.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: There are practices involved such as: washing of the body, funeral rites, prayers and interment.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: Cenotaphs are not a feature of Ifa tradition.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: Domestic burials may take place in rural settings but not a common practice in modern times.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Yes

Notes: There are burials of kings, diviners and elders. These burials may differ in ritual patters.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are present in Ifa religion.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Olodumare is the supreme being in Ifa religion.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: Olodumare in Ifa/Yoruba religion is not conceived as having human form. He is often depicted as being transcendent, endowed with authority and the creator of the world as well as humanbeings.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: He is often associated with heaven or above the sky.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: Olodumare, the supreme God is not chthonic , he is transcendent and not the deity of the underworld.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: Monarchs are powerful and sacred but are not equated to Olodumare the Supreme being in Ifa religion.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: In Ifa tradition, the monarch is not a manifestation or emanation of the high God, he is rather a sacred human legitimized by divine order.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The Supreme being is not seen as having human kinship with elites.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: All humans are equal before the Supreme being in Ifa religion. All individuals are seen as God's creation.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme being is perfect.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Transcendence, Immanence, the ultimate authority, the beginning and end of all things, the most powerful and accessible through divination

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the attributes of the supreme being in Ifa/Yoruba religion include his Omni science, omnipresence and omnipotence

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The Supreme God's knowledge is not limited. His knowledge is universal.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The Supreme being's knowledge is not restricted to specific areas or region. His knowledge is unlimited.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: His knowledge is not described as unrestricted within a sample region.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: The supreme being's knowledge is described in terms of being restricted or unrestricted by regions. He is believed to be everywhere.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme being has complete knowledge of all things so he has full grasp of the seen and unseen.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme has a knowledge of everything including things done in private or in the dark.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, the Supreme being sees everything including thoughts, intentions and hidden motives.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme being knows a person's true character.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, the Supreme being is believed to have knowledge of all future occurrences as well as the present and past.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, the supreme being has all knowledge of this world and beyond.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Olodumare is understood in Ifa religion to have the power to intentionally make things happen in the world.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, the supreme being has the power to reward people with blessings.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Just as the Supreme rewards good deed, he punishes wrong doings and allows consequences for bad actions.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Olodumare is understood to have indirect causal efficacy in the world.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme being exhibits positive emotion through the approval and blessings of good actions by individuals.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Olodumare expresses negative emotions in cases of wrongdoings or immorality.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: Hunger is a physical human need. In Ifa religion, the Supreme being does not possess hunger.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: In Yoruba religion, other supernatural beings called divinities (orisa) may be worshipped but Olodumare is the head.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: transcendence, Omniscience, Invisibility and formlessness, Omnipresent, Perfect and timelessness

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme God communicates with the living through indirect means such as divination, dreams, visions and trances.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: This happens indirectly.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Dreams are means through which the Supreme communicates warnings and guidance with people.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Just like through dreams, the Supreme being uses trances as a means of communication.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Divination is one key method through which the supreme being guides people.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Though religious specialists play major roles in divine communication, there are other means the supreme God relates to people.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: Monarchs are seen as custodians of spiritual authority but in Ifa religion, divine communication is not limited to them.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: Through divinities, ancestors (egungun) and ritual objects.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits exist in the spiritual realm.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: They are not seen in a physical sense but may be seen in dreams or in spiritual sense.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits are not felt physically in terms of touch but they can be felt spiritually.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Human spirits do not have knowledge restricted to a specific domain.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Human spirits are not understood as having knowledge restricted to a specific area. They are only aware of situations relating to their family and descendants

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, human spirits' knowledge is focused on family and descendants.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits can influence or affect the lives of their families and descendants through spiritual means.

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits are believed to be able to bless, protect, guide and support family members that honour them

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Apart from being able to reward, human spirits have the power to punish, harm and curse family members who do not reverence them.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Human Spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world through spiritual means rather than physical means.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits are believed to have memory of their past life and family relations.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, human spirits do not exhibit positive emotions physically but show positive responses towards the living by blessing, protecting and encouragement especially when honoured.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits may show negative emotion through responses that can happen as withdrawal of blessings and protection when they feel neglected or disrespected.

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

Notes: Human spirits are non physical entities and hunger is a physical need .

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: They possess communication abilities, moral connection and memory.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa belief, human spirits may communicate with the living through dreams, visions, divination and trances.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits can communicate in everyday life through signs and events rather than directly.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: in Ifa religion, human spirits can give instructions and guidance through dreams.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa belief, trance possession is a means by which human spirits communicate with the living.

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: Ifa divination is a key method by which human spirits communicate with the living.

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: Religious specialists play key roles in divination but there are other means such as dreams and trances that human spirits can communicate with the living.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: Kings are important in ritual but they are not the only means for communication with ancestors.

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: Other means of communication include: signs, feelings and rituals.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: There are non supernatural beings in Ifa religion and they play a major role in the belief system.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: They cannot be seen physically .

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: They can be felt but not physically. They may create a strong sense of presence during ritual activities.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Non human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion non human supernatural beings do not knowledge restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Non human supernatural beings do not have knowledge restricted to specific areas within the sample region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, non human supernatural beings are not understood in terms of regional knowledge limits.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, non human supernatural beings are not understood in terms of knowledge being unrestricted by regions.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa belief, they observe human behaviour and check morality though not physically but in spiritual sense.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Though not physically seen, they are believed to be aware of human actions in public and private places.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, non human supernatural being have the power to know a person's thought and hidden motives.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Non human supernatural beings are believed to know a person's basic character or personal essence.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: They have the knowledge or insight into future events and know what will happen to a person in relation to destiny.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: They are aware of human actions and the society

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Non human supernatural beings can intentionally influence human life and events.

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Non human supernatural beings can bless , grant good health, fertility, prosperity and success. These are only granted to individuals who worship, offer sacrifices and are respect them.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Non human supernatural beings can punish when their rules are broken. They may punish through misfortune, illness, setbacks and pain.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Non human supernatural beings are believed to have indirect causal efficacy in the world.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: When they are properly honoured, they get happy and satisfaction when they are properly worshipped. They also bestow kindness, blessings, protection and success toward devotees.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, non human supernatural beings may exhibit negative emotions in cases of wrong doings and disrespect. They express displeasure by withdrawing favour, blessings, protection, sound health and success from devotees.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: They may require sacrifices in form of food when hungry.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: They serve as custodians of morality, mediators and Olodumare's deputies.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, humans are distinct from divine. Orisa are different from human and non human spiritual beings.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ifa religious system includes a variety of supernatural beings such as the supreme being (Olodumare), Divinities (orisa), spirits, ancestors and mysterious powers.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: Ifa religion is not organized by kinship or a family model but spiritual roles and functions.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, the supernatural world has a hierarchical structure with the supreme being at the top, next to the divinities, to spirits, ancestors and mysterious power.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: The powers of non human supernatural beings are generally domain specific.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: Supreme being Divinities Spirits Ancestors Mysterious powers (magic and medicine)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion supernatural monitoring is present. The supreme being is aware of everything, Orisas check human actions and ancestors are believed to be in charge of their families.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion there is supernatural monitoring of human adherence to social norms with either consequences or blessings attached to actions.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are believed to care about taboos and violations usually attract consequences.

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, certain orisa are associated with food taboos called ewo.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, certain spaces must not be profaned. Going against this may attract severe consequences.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa, certain objects are sacred or spiritually charged. They must be handled in specific ways to avoid spiritual consequences.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: Other taboos include: behaviour, speech, ritual and social taboos.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, killing a member of one's community is a serious offence that attracts severe punishment.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa, taking a human life is seen as violation regardless if they are members of other religion. Human life is viewed as sacred and spiritually significant.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are believed to care about the murder of people from other polities because human life is sacred.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa, supernatural beings care about sexual behaviour as it is linked to morality and spirituality.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa belief system, adultery violates moral, social and spiritual order and thus has consequences attached to it.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, incest is forbidden and attracts spiritual consequences.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: Other sexual practices that supernatural beings forbid include: rape, bestiality and sexual activities that violate sacred times.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, lying attracts spiritual consequences and affects trust as well as social harmony.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, supernatural beings care about the honouring of oaths because they are sacred commitments that are connected to morality and religiosity.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Neglect of responsibility is not acceptable in Ifa religion. This is because one of the core values of Ifa religion is diligence.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are believed to care about sorcery especially when it is used to harm others or for any other negative purpose.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings do not support lethal fighting as it is a threat to social harmony and

violation of good character.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings disapprove of shirking risk as it promotes avoiding responsibilities and obligations.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion respect for elders is central to Yoruba value. Disrespecting elders is an offense and violation of good character.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings do not support gossiping.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings disapprove of property crimes.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, supernatural beings attach importance to ritual observance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about the performance of rituals such as prayer, offerings, sacrifices, purification, divination and festivals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings in Ifa belief do not generally care about conversion of non religionists but they are rather concerned about ritual activities, good behaviours and positive human relationship.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are believed to care about economic fairness. This is why in Ifa religion justice, fairness, honesty and equality are often emphasized.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene, ritual purity, respect for sacredness and good conduct especially when related ritual cleanliness.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: yes

Notes: Others include hospitality, generosity, justice, integrity, humility and environmental respect.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are believed to mete out punishment.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, the cause of punishment is known through divination.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, punishment is not only done by high God. Orisas, spirits and ancestors can punish offenders.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, punishment is carried out by many supernatural beings including the supreme being, divinities and ancestors.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: Punishment is not mainly seen as an impersonal cause and effect system.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, the reason for punishment is known through divination.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, punishment is believed to help enforce proper religious ritual and devotional adherence.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Group norms such as morality, respect and social responsibility are often promoted through punishment.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is believed to help inhibit selfishness and encourage good morals such as justice, fairness and generosity

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: In Ifa belief, supernatural punishment is not done randomly.

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: Supernatural punishments in Ifa belief is not only meted out in afterlife but it is experienced in the present world through misfortunes, hardship, sickness and loss.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa supernatural punishment are meted out in this lifetime and the consequences appear in form of misfortune, bad luck, illness and death.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishments in this life are often emphasized in Ifa religion.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: Bad luck is an example of punishment in Ifa belief.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment in this life can come in form of political failure.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: people can face defeat in battle as a form of punishment.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: Crop failure and bad weather are clear examples of supernatural punishment.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: Punishment in this life can happen in form of disaster in journey.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Mild sensory displeasure can be a consequence for violation of taboos.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment in this life can consist of extreme sensory displeasure especially when it involves violation of taboos.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Sicknesses are examples of punishment in this life.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: Infertility, miscarriages and difficulty conceiving are examples of punishment in this life.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes some punishment do not end with an individual, it may be extended to descendants.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Punishments in this life could come in other forms such as : financial hardship, stagnation and loss of protection.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa belief, supernatural beings are believed to reward good deeds.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: The cause and purpose of supernatural rewards are considered knowable and are often connected to good behaviour and ritual compliance.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Supernatural rewards are not only done by high God.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Rewards often come from many supernatural beings including the Supreme being, Divinities , Spirits and Ancestors.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, supernatural rewards are not totally explained as an impersonal cause and effect system.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa belief, supernatural reward helps to encourage ritual compliance and devotional adherence.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, supernatural rewards are believed promote group norms by encouraging behaviours that contribute to moral and social stability.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural rewards are believed to discourage selfishness and promote good character and generosity.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, supernatural rewards are not done randomly.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: Supernatural rewards are mainly given in the afterlife. Some rewards also experienced in the present life as well.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural rewards in this life time are believed to come as blessing, good health, progress, protection, fertility and success.

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized in Ifa religious group.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: Good luck is an example of reward in this life.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: Reward can appear in form of political success and power.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Success in battle is considered a reward in this life.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: Reward in this life consist of healthy crops and good weather.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: Success on journey is an example of reward in this life.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Notes: Rewards in this life are often likened to broader life blessings such as sound health, success and protection. They are not mainly understood as mild sensory pleasure.

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Notes: Rewards in this life are often likened to broader life blessings such as sound health, success and protection. They are not mainly understood as extreme sensory pleasure.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: Sound health is a reward in this life.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: Fertility, pregnancy and family lineage continuation are forms of supernatural reward in this life.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Fortunes extended to descendants are rewards in this life.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Other earthly rewards include family harmony, protection, fulfilment of destiny and wisdom.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa belief, many general social norms are intertwined to religious teachings. These norms include good character, respect for elders, integrity and fairness.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a slight distinction between moral and conventional norms but both often overlap as they are both spiritually significant.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa belief, specifically moral norms are clearly prescribed and emphasized within the religious tradition. An example is good character (Iwa pele)

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa belief, moral norms are often implicitly linked to broader, flexible metaphysical concepts such as destiny.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Notes: In Ifa belief, specifically moral norms are not usually explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, moral norms are not linked to impersonal cosmic order like karma

but to spiritual forces like Olodumare, Orisa and Ori.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion, moral norms are linked to anthropomorphic beings especially through divinities and ancestor who interact morally with humans.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

Notes: Specifically moral norms are not linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic beings as it is in other religious traditions such as Judaism, Christianity and Islam.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Notes: Moral norms have a connection to metaphysical in Ifa belief.

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: In Ifa belief, membership does not require celibacy or full sexual abstinence.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: In Ifa religious belief membership does not require partial sexual abstinence. it is not a general requirement.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: In Ifa belief, membership does not require castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: It is not a general requirement in Ifa religion.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: It is not a general requirement in Ifa belief system.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: In Ifa tradition, membership does not involve permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory

painful wounds:

– No

Notes: This is not a general requirement in Ifa religion.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, membership does not require the sacrifice of an adult or any human being.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, membership does not require the sacrifice of children or any other person.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, membership does not require self sacrifice which involves physical harm or self injury. Self discipline may be required but not loss of ones life.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Membership in Ifa religion does not require sacrifice of property or valuable items.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Membership does not require a permanent sacrifice of time but it involves commitments to services, prayer, festivals etc.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: In Ifa belief, membership does not require physical risk taking as a condition of belonging.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Membership does require accepting and following ethical precepts.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, membership does not require the marginalization by out group members or outsiders.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Membership in Ifa religion involves some form of participation in small scale rituals but this depends on the person's role and level.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 24

Notes: No strict time intervals are fixed between rituals. However, priests and devotees who have an altar to the oracle or other altars in their homes are required to pour libation to the oracle or consult them daily or as often as they can do.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, membership does not require participation in large scale rituals.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: There are extra in group markers present such as ritual practices, signs and actions.

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, tattoos are not a required marker for membership.

↳ Circumcision:

– No

Notes: Circumcision is not a religious requirement for membership in Ifa religious tradition.

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa religion food taboos exist but not a requirement for membership.

↳ Hair:

– No

Notes: Hair is not a required ritual marker for membership in Ifa religion.

↳ Dress:

– No

Notes: membership does not require a specific dress code but they may be required to wear certain outfits for rituals. This is usually white apparel.

↳ Ornaments:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religion, this is not a general requirement for membership but they may serve as ritual markers for some devotees.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa practice, archaic ritual language is present. It may include chants, prayers and divination recitation.

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: In Ifa, fictive kinship terminology is frequently used.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

Notes: Fictive kinship terminology is not universal.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: Fictive kinship terminology to an extent is widespread in Ifa religious group.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: In Ifa religious tradition, fictive terminology is commonly used. it is a feature of Ifa religion.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A religious idea or group. Although centuries ago, Ifa religion was a heritage of the Yoruba people, today there are adherents of the religion across the world. The group in Ibadan is just one of the several

groups spread across the world.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: There is no provision of institutionalized famine relief.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Famine relief is not available to the group's adherents through other institution.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Ifa religion supports poverty relief for devotees.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Poverty relief is not available to devotees through institutions other than the Ifa religious group.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: There is provision of institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Care for the elderly and infirm is available through institutions outside Ifa religious group.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Ifa group does not provide formal education to the adherents. Instead of formal schooling, learning takes place through apprenticeship and divination training.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Formal education is available to adherents through other institutions such as public schools, universities and private educational systems.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: The group adherents do not interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: The group does not provide public food storage.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Public food storage is provided by external institutions such as NGOs and government agencies.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide water management infrastructure such as irrigation. These are primarily handled by engineering companies through public funds or funded by multinational institutions

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water management is provided to the adherents through institutions such as the government .

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: The group does not provide transportation infrastructure.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Transportation infrastructure is provided by external institutions such as the government.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not levy taxes or tithes. Financial support is not compulsory.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group

in question:

– Yes

Notes: Taxes are levied on adherents by external institutions such as the government. Taxes are not levied by Ifa religious group.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide institutionalized police force.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group adherents interact with institutionalized police forces provided by external institutions.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: The group does not provide institutionalized judges.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents interact with institutionalized judicial systems provided by external institutions,

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: The group does not enforce institutionalized punishment.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents are subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by external state legal system.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Execution is part of institutionalized punishments in legal system.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: Exile is not one of the institutionalized punishments in the country's legal system.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Corporal punishment is part of institutionalized punishments in legal system.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Notes: Ostracism is not one of the institutionalized punishments in the country's legal system.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Seizure of property can be part of institutionalized punishments in legal system.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not have a formal legal code. it is based on oral tradition.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents are subject to formal legal codes provided by the state institutions.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: The group does not have an institutionalized military.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents may participate in institutionalized military provided by the State.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents are protected and subject to institutionalized military forces provided by the State.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The group does not possess its own distinct written language. The group uses Yoruba language for religious transmission.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Non religion specific written language is available to adherents through external institutions such as school.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents use non religion specific written language through external institutions such as school.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not possess a formal calendar but the group has fixed times in the year for the celebration of festivals.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Formal calendars are provided by external institutions such as the government. The group plans its programmes around the Gregorian calendar in use in their region.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide food as an institution.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Although there are farmers among the group members, food is also bought from markets, provided by other farmers, humanitarian initiatives and government organized programs.

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Ifa Religious Group in Ibadan, Neimark, Philip . *The Way of the Orisa: Empowering Your Life Through the Ancient African Religious of Ifa*. San Francisco: Harper, 1993.

Reference: Ifa Religious Group in Ibadan, Oládúnkẹ, Aransi Ayoola. "Ifa Literary Corpus: A Philosophical Exposition of Economic Sustainability in Yoruba Society" 6, no. 1 (February 28, 2025). <https://doi.org/10.31248/ijah2025.192>.

Reference: Ifa Religious Group in Ibadan, Okudolo, Ikemefuna, Victor Ojakorotu, and Matthew Oni. "Inculcating Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS) Philosophy of Odu Ifa Corpus into Contemporary Politico-administrative Governance Practices of Africa" 6, no. 4 (December 1, 2025). <https://doi.org/10.31920/2634-7644/2025/v6n4a14>.